

Expunged, Yet Excluded: Reconsidering Criminal Record Discrimination in South African Employment Law in *O'Connor v LexisNexis (Pty) Ltd (2024)* 45 ILJ 1287 (LC)

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South African society is characterised by endemic inequality, which is the result of past discriminatory practices. Hence, the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996 prohibits unfair discrimination. The Labour Court's judgment under analysis in *O'Connor v LexisNexis (Pty) Ltd (2024) 45 ILJ 1287 (LC)*, which addresses the intersection of employment equity, criminal history and the constitutional right to dignity, falls within the category of unfair discrimination. The court was tasked with determining whether the retraction of a job offer because O'Connor had an expunged criminal record constituted unfair discrimination under section 6 of the Employment Equity Act 55 of 1998 (EEA). While the court declined to enforce the employment contract through specific performance, it affirmed that excluding a job candidate on the basis of a decades-old, expunged conviction, particularly where the criminal history was irrelevant to the job, amounted to unfair discrimination. This commentary critiques the court's dual-track reasoning that upheld the contractual condition while simultaneously condemning the employer's discriminatory rationale. The analysis also addresses the limitations of the court's interpretation of expungement and calls for doctrinal clarity in reconciling labour law, human dignity and reintegration of criminal offenders.

Keywords: Unfair discrimination, expunged criminal records, systemic exclusions, inherent requirements of the job

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996 (hereafter the Constitution) proscribes direct or indirect discrimination. Section 9(3) provides that the state may not unfairly discriminate directly or indirectly against anyone on one or more grounds, including race, gender, sex, pregnancy, marital status, ethnic or social origin, colour, sexual orientation, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, language and birth (Constitution). Neither the Constitution nor the Employment Equity Act 55 of 1998 (EEA) lists criminal record as a ground of discrimination. People with criminal records find it extremely difficult to obtain employment (Mujuzi & Tseled, 2014). Candidates for employment with criminal records have limited opportunities for employment, even if their convictions have been expunged (Mujuzi & Tseled, 2014, p 244). Thus, individuals with criminal records form a marginalised category of jobseekers who are subjected to systemic and often unjust exclusion or discrimination even after their convictions are expunged. In simple terms, expungement means erasing a criminal record, effectively making it inaccessible to the public.

The only time such silent discrimination comes to light is when it is subject to judicial scrutiny. The judgment in *O'Connor v LexisNexis (Pty) Ltd* is one of a few recent adjudicated cases. This

judgment highlights the dynamic between the employer's prerogative to screen or vet any candidate for employment and a person's constitutional right to pursue economic activity of his or her choice and benefit from the rehabilitation process emanating from the expungement of a criminal record (para 84).

At the core of the case is the question of whether an expunged criminal conviction disqualifies a candidate from employment, especially when such a conviction is not an inherent requirement of the job or is irrelevant to the job performance. The decision addresses this sensitive issue by acknowledging that discrimination based on criminal background may be arbitrary and unjust if not directly related to the position (para 88). This case note explores how the court applied and interpreted the EEA and the Constitution.

Factual Background

In December 2023, the respondent, LexisNexis (Pty) Ltd, advertised a position of 'Senior Data Discovery and Enrichment Expert I' in its taxonomy team. The job mainly entailed organising and classifying legal and academic content for the company's digital platforms. Mr O'Connor, the applicant (O'Connor), a qualified professional with extensive experience in data enrichment and digital content classification, applied for the position. Following a successful interview, LexisNexis requested that the O'Connor complete a 'RefCheck Consent and Indemnity Form'. In this form, the O'Connor disclosed that, although he had a criminal record from a 2001 charge, the conviction had been expunged. On 21 January 2024, he submitted the form and did a fingerprint verification shortly thereafter to facilitate the background check.

LexisNexis, on 29 January 2024, conditionally offered O'Connor the position subject to a criminal background check, verified

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credentials and a positive reference. On the same day, O'Connor accepted the offer, and the employment contract was signed electronically by both parties the following day, i.e., on 30 January 2024. Giving effect to the employment contract, LexisNexis granted the O'Connor access to its 'work day schedule portal'. The role was entirely remote, and O'Connor was to work from his home in Komani (formerly Queenstown) (para 89). On the strength of the job offer, O'Connor resigned from his previous position, closed his private consultancy, and invested in home-office infrastructure, including internet upgrades and a backup power supply. However, LexisNexis, on 6 February 2024, retracted the job offer. LexisNexis alluded to the background check, which revealed six counts of theft, one count of fraud, and two counts of defeating the ends of justice (para 11).

In response, O'Connor explained that the convictions had taken place some two decades earlier and had been expunged. LexisNexis did not heed his plea for an opportunity to explain. Left with no choice, O'Connor then referred a dispute to the Commission for Conciliation, Mediation and Arbitration (CCMA). Following failed conciliation and the issuance of a certificate of non-resolution, O'Connor brought an urgent application before the Labour Court, seeking relief based on unfair dismissal, breach of contract and unfair discrimination.

The case raised four interlinked questions: (i) whether a criminal record constitutes an arbitrary ground of unfair discrimination under section 6 of the EEA and section 187(1)(f) of the Labour Relations Act 66 of 1995 (LRA), (ii) whether expunged convictions legally render a criminal history irrelevant for employment; (iii) whether an LexisNexis can validly retract an offer due to a not-entirely-clear criminal check despite expungement, and (iv) whether a criminal record relates to an 'inherent requirement' of the job, justifying exclusion? Simply put, the Labour Court had to decide, among others, whether LexisNexis' conduct constituted an automatically unfair dismissal based on an arbitrary ground due to past criminal convictions within the meaning of s 187(1)(f) of the LRA (para 15).

As the matter was brought on an urgent basis, the court had to determine whether O'Connor met the test of urgency justifying departing from the normal court processes. The court relied on the two-legged test: (i) whether substantial redress would not be possible in the ordinary course, and (ii) whether any prejudice to LexisNexis or the court precluded urgency, such as the issue of self-created urgency, any procedural prejudice that might befall LexisNexis, and any prejudice to the administration of justice (para 21). O'Connor demonstrated that urgent relief was warranted; otherwise, it would result in severe personal hardship, including loss of shelter and inability to care for his ill mother. The court rejected LexisNexis' claims of delay, finding that O'Connor had pursued conciliation in good faith and had acted promptly thereafter (paras 19-20).

Turning to the urgency of the specific performance claim, the court acknowledged that specific performance has regularly been granted on an urgent basis (para 34). O'Connor claimed that he had concluded a binding employment contract and, based on it, resigned from his previous employment and incurred expenses. He claimed further that LexisNexis' alleged repudiation had left him in a worse position than a dismissed employee, causing severe financial and personal hardship. The court rejected the argument that financial hardship alone cannot create urgency. It ruled that, if damages cannot adequately redress the harm later, urgency is justified (paras 35-36).

In all, the court ruled that O'Connor's claim for specific performance was inherently urgent, as the consequences of delay would cause irreparable harm, and monetary damages in due course would be insufficient redress. The claim was lodged timeously, the prejudice to LexisNexis was limited, and the circumstances justified deviation from normal procedural timelines (para 45).

As regards discrimination and expungement, the court shifted focus to section 6 of the EEA, which prohibits direct or indirect unfair discrimination on listed grounds or any other arbitrary grounds (paras 47-48). This is so because the adoption of the EEA was premised on the understanding that apartheid and other discriminatory laws and practices created employment, occupation and income disparities within the national labour market. These disparities disadvantaged mainly black people and such disadvantage could not be redressed simply by repealing discriminatory laws (para 82). To this end, the legislator enacted the EEA to promote the right to equality in the workplace by, among others, eliminating unfair discrimination in employment.

The court found that discrimination based on a past, expunged criminal record can impair a person's dignity and equal worth, particularly where the record has no bearing on the job. Citing *Harksen v Lane NO 1998 (1) SA 300 (CC) (Harksen)* and *Naidoo and Others v Parliament of the Republic of SA (2020) 41 ILJ 1931 (LAC) (Naidoo)*, the court affirmed that arbitrary grounds of unfair discrimination encompass not only irrational exclusions but also those that affect fundamental human dignity (paras 83-84). The decision acknowledged that expungement, while not erasing a criminal record 'for all purposes' (para 69), serves as evidence of rehabilitation. By relying on the now-expunged convictions in circumstances where they bear no material relevance to the job, LexisNexis' conduct amounted to discrimination (para 94).

This finding led the court to examine whether it was an inherent requirement of the job that O'Connor had a clean criminal record. This was necessary because the inherent requirements of the job and affirmative action are two exceptions that can justify discriminatory action by an employer. In other words, discrimination is fair if the reasons for discriminating are based on the inherent requirements of the job or affirmative action (section 6(2)(b) of EEA).

Thus, in terms of section 6(2)(b) of the EEA, discrimination is not unfair when related to an inherent requirement of the job. The court examined the nature of the work O'Connor would perform, i.e., he was to be involved in the digital classification of legal texts and was to conduct his work remotely. The court found that, in such circumstances, there appeared to be no justification for requiring a 'clear' criminal record (para 89). Moreover, the work required no exercise of a fiduciary duty and did not involve control of finances or sensitive client information that would require a clean record to be an inherent requirement of the job, thereby disqualifying anyone with prior convictions (para 88). The court was satisfied that LexisNexis had failed to provide evidence connecting the applicant's earlier convictions to the core functions of the position. Thus, the court found that O'Connor's prior criminal record was immaterial to the inherent requirements of the role, rendering his exclusion from the position arbitrary and discriminatory (para 81).

Critical Analysis

As a landmark decision in South African employment law, this judgment addresses the legal implications of retracting a job offer solely on the basis of a past criminal record, even though

it has been expunged. The Labour Court had to decide whether the O'Connor's criminal past was a necessary condition or an inherent requirement for the job in question and whether LexisNexis' retraction of a job offer amounted to unfair discrimination under section 6 of the EEA.

As stated above, the court found that the retraction of the job offer amounted to unfair discrimination because O'Connor's convictions had been expunged. In finding so, the court took into account the fact that the convictions had no bearing on the position. The court's judgment strongly buttresses the right to dignity and equality entrenched in the Constitution. The judgment further embodies the rehabilitation process that underscores the constitutional restorative principle in post-apartheid South Africa. Section 23 of the Constitution encourages everyone to freely engage in a remunerative profession, and this note argues that 'everyone' includes all those whose convictions have been expunged.

This judgment was delivered at a time when South Africa's unemployment rate in Q4 of 2024 reportedly stood at 31.9% (<https://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=18028>, 2025). This rate reflects the difficulty South Africans have in securing jobs. This difficulty in securing jobs is even more acute for people with criminal records. Mujuzi and Tsweledi (2014) argue that a person with a criminal record may never be offered a job before the record in question has been expunged, or he or she may never work at all until his or her death, in cases where the person does not qualify to have his or her criminal record expunged. Worst, the authors argue that even those who have been rehabilitated face a similar fate. It is apparent that employers are wary of employing persons with criminal records due to fear of liability and the social stigma that frequently attaches to formerly incarcerated people (Westrope, 1973).

This issue has also been subject to debate in other jurisdictions. For instance, in the United States, the criminal justice system excludes convicted people, mainly people of colour, from employment (Smith & Simon, 2020). This exclusion reduces employment prospects for people with a criminal record, and, as a consequence, they are exploited in the labour market, having to accept jobs with meagre wages. From the above, it appears that the US criminal justice system operates as a gatekeeper and enforcer for the precarious situation of convicts in the labour market. Thus, the system entrenches social and racial inequality, producing a surplus labour pool, especially within marginalised communities (Smith & Simon, 2020, p 4).

Hence, in holding that the exclusion of persons based on expunged criminal records constitutes unfair discrimination, particularly when such records are unrelated to the job, the judgment promotes a more inclusive and socially just attitude to employment. The court's reliance on *Harksen v Lane* and *Naidoo v Parliament* aligns with a human rights-based paradigm that recognises rehabilitation as a constitutional imperative, not a mere policy option.

Importantly, the court acknowledges the enduring stigma attached to criminal records and the societal obstacles experienced by those who have served their sentences and been granted legal expungement. The court views this sort of discrimination as a violation of dignity, which militates against South Africa's broader constitutional narrative that seeks to dismantle barriers to reintegration and to foster a second opportunity as part of a transformative justice agenda. This approach resonates with the

restorative vision embedded in the White Paper on Corrections of 2005. The White Paper remains one of the policy documents that serves as the backbone of governmental plans relating to the sentencing and rehabilitation of offenders. The White Paper (2005, p 7) seeks to foster rehabilitation over punishment and calls for the implementation of appropriate programmes, so that people who leave correctional centres have appropriate attitudes and competencies enabling them to successfully integrate back into society as law-abiding and productive citizens.

It is exactly because offenders have been rehabilitated that they need societal support for their reintegration, and securing jobs is part of this process. Hence, employment is key for the reintegration of past offenders, especially because employment has been shown to reduce recidivism (Naylor & Heydon, 2022).

Where a former convict does not secure employment due to his criminal record, he or she may face difficulties and, in a case such as the one discussed in this note, the threat of homelessness, loss of livelihood and inability to provide care for family members. Such a person runs the risk of returning to crime merely to survive. Moreover, the reintegration envisaged in the White Paper would remain illusory. In considering these circumstances, the court affirmed that access to employment is not just a commodity but a recipe for personal development, freedom, family support, and societal participation.

The court's ruling also contributes to developing a jurisprudence that recognises entrenched structural disadvantages. While the EEA mainly prohibits discrimination based on listed grounds such as race, age, political opinion and gender, the court's preparedness to rule that reliance on a person's criminal record is an arbitrary ground of unfair discrimination rooted in the right to dignity demonstrates a positive step towards the development of an understanding of vulnerability and exclusion in labour markets marred by unemployment. This illustrates the evolving nature of constitutional interpretation and reflects the extant realities of many South Africans who have experienced historical marginalisation, systemic poverty and criminalisation.

In doing so, the court acknowledges that the objectives of employment equity are not only to restore the human dignity of those who have historically been excluded not just by law, but by deeply embedded social biases held by those who frown upon persons with criminal records. Employers, the courts and society at large are urged to renounce punitive or stigmatising tendencies and adopt inclusive and fair policies that respect the letter and spirit of the Constitution.

The Court's Incorrect Interpretation of Expungement

Despite setting the record straight that exclusion based on an expunged criminal record amounts to unfair discrimination, the court's treatment of expungement reveals interpretive uncertainty. While acknowledging that expungement under section 271B of the Criminal Procedure Act 51 of 1977 (CPA) evinced rehabilitation, the court nevertheless declined to interpret it as erasing the legal existence of a conviction (para 68). In fact, the court upheld LexisNexis' view that the criminal check was not 'clear'. In so doing, the court drew a distinction between expungement under the CPA and amnesty under the Promotion of National Unity and Reconciliation Act 34 of 1995, arguing that the former did not render convictions void for all legal purposes (para 69).

This stance grants an employer the discretion to treat an expunged conviction as a barrier to employment, provided the offer of employment is conditional and the background check reveals a record. Hence, the court ruled that the expungement of O'Connor's criminal record had no bearing on the job, justifying the non-retraction of the offer. Had the job been related to a position of trust, the court would have upheld the retraction of the offer (para 87).

It is at this juncture that this note argues that the court's decision to reject O'Connor's claim for specific performance is legally unsound. The court found that the employment agreement included a resolute condition requiring 'criminal checks being clear' (paras 62-71). Although the O'Connor's criminal record had been expunged, the court reasoned that expungement in terms of the Criminal Procedure Act did not erase the existence of prior convictions for all legal purposes, including contract law. On this basis, the court accepted LexisNexis' contention that an expunged record did not satisfy the requirement of a 'clear' criminal check, which meant an individual with no history of criminal convictions whatsoever. Consequently, LexisNexis' invocation of the resolute condition was valid, and O'Connor's claim for specific performance had to fail.

This note argues that the court could not simultaneously dismiss O'Connor's claim for specific performance while upholding a resolute condition that subsequently underpinned a finding of unfair discrimination. A resolute condition cannot be legally valid if its underlying rationale is itself invalid. Given that the court determined that the retraction of the offer constituted discrimination on an arbitrary ground, the note contends that the resolute condition pertaining to the reference check could not legally be sustained. The court's judgment to uphold the claim for specific performance was, in fact, grounded in its finding that the reason for the retraction was discriminatory. The note, therefore, argues that the court's pirouette to discard and then use the discarded element distorts the conceptual mechanism, purpose and meaning of expungement. There are serious constitutional and policy issues with this approach. If expungement is a legal mechanism intended to erase criminal records, ease the reintegration of and provide protection from the enduring consequences of past criminal conduct to rehabilitated persons, then treating such criminal records as functionally existent for employment vetting purposes contradicts the spirit of the legislation. It also invites divergent practices among employers and undermines the certainty that expungement is designed to provide.

Furthermore, this position distorts the rehabilitative objectives promoted in South African correctional and reintegration policies. Indeed, the White Paper on Corrections expressly promotes reintegration as the ultimate purpose of corrections, envisioning a system where former offenders are restored to society. By allowing LexisNexis to withdraw employment offers based on expunged records, the court undermines these restorative objectives.

The court might have drawn more strongly on the values-based reasoning shown in cases such as *Hoffmann v South African Airways* 2001 (1) SA 1 (CC); (2000) 21 ILJ 2357 (CC); [2000] 12 BLLR 1365 (CC) and *S v Makwanyane* 1995 (3) SA 391 (CC); 1995 (6) BCLR 665 para 312 where the Constitutional Court valued dignity, transformation and non-discrimination in interpreting legislation (para 312). A purposive approach could have led the court to treat expungement as creating a legal fiction that erases convictions, i.e., convictions no longer exist for all employment-related purposes, subject only to statutory, expressly stated exceptions. Thus, the note argues that the court missed an opportunity to provide a principled

framework for differentiating between legitimate integrity screening and unlawful discrimination. A more robust judicial interpretation would have clarified, for instance, whether the consideration of expunged convictions as grounds for exclusion constitutes indirect discrimination. In fact, this note contends that a finding on discrimination based exclusively on arbitrariness fails to address the core issue at hand. More importantly, the main question lies in categorising the systemic exclusion of people with a criminal record from employment opportunities.

The note argues that such exclusion constitutes a form of indirect discrimination. The determination of whether this discrimination is fair or not should be guided by the principle elaborated in *Harksen*. In *Harksen*, the Constitutional Court established a structured three-stage test for determining unfair discrimination claims. The first stage of the enquiry involves determining whether the conduct subject to the dispute amounts to a differentiation. If this enquiry finds differentiation, the next stage entails a two-stage analysis: (i) whether the differentiation amounts to discrimination and, if so, (ii) whether the discrimination is unfair (paras 43-53).

If the differentiation is based on one of the prohibited grounds of discrimination listed in the Constitution, the LRA or the EEA, not only will discrimination have been established but the unfairness thereof is presumed. However, where the differentiation is on an unlisted ground, the applicant bears the *onus* to establish the discrimination and the unfairness thereof (McGregor, 2021, p 68). Once the discrimination is found to be unfair, then a determination will have to be made as to whether the provision can be justified under the limitations clause in the Constitution.

Applying *Harksen's* approach in this case, LexisNexis' conduct of retracting the offer based on O'Connor's expunged record differentiated between individuals with prior convictions and those without prior convictions, including those whose convictions had been expunged. This differentiation amounted to discrimination. The unfairness of the discrimination stemmed from the fact that the exclusion bore no rational connection to the inherent requirements of the job (which would have been a reasonable justification for exclusion of the applicant in terms of section 6(2) of the EEA). There was, therefore, no reasonable explanation why O'Connor's job offer was rescinded.

This conduct by LexisNexis, the note argues, amounted to indirect discrimination. This is so because indirect discrimination occurs when an apparent neutral criterion is applied, but it negatively and disproportionately affects a certain group (McGregor, 2021, p 61). Within the South African context, the affected group is the 'designated groups' defined in section 1 of the EEA, which are black people, women and people with disabilities.

Indirect discrimination is more often disguised, i.e., not as easily discernible as direct discrimination, where certain characteristics or features are the basis for the discrimination (McGregor, 2021, p 61). The prevalence of unfair discrimination in South Africa is the vestige of the apartheid discriminatory practices, which discriminated against the black majority population. This societal scourge transcended all spheres, including the workplace. Hence, the EEA was enacted to 'achieve equity in the workplace by promoting equal opportunity and fair treatment in employment through the elimination of unfair discrimination'.

To achieve this purpose section 6(1) of the EEA prohibits unfair discrimination by asserting that 'no person may unfairly discriminate, directly or indirectly, against an employee, in any

employment policy or practice, on one or more grounds, including race, gender, sex, pregnancy, marital status, family responsibility, ethnic or social origin, colour, sexual orientation, age, disability, religion, HIV status, conscience, belief, political opinion, culture, language, birth or on any other arbitrary ground'. Section 5 of the EEA enjoins every employer to eliminate any unfair discrimination in any employment policy or practice and to promote equality of opportunity in the workplace.

Because a person with a criminal record is not on the listed grounds nor included in the designated groups, this note contends that the exclusion of such a person from employment opportunity amounts to indirect discrimination. This note argues that persons with a criminal record represent a significant marginalised group who are deprived of employment opportunities, thereby perpetuating patterns of systemic discrimination. This marginalised group comprises people of all races, with the commonality being their criminal record. Their exclusion infringes human dignity and undermines the principle of substantive equality that underpins South Africa's constitutional framework, particularly when it is not justified by the inherent requirements of the job.

If the exclusion of people with expunged criminal records is not categorised as indirect unfair discrimination, the expungement will merely be a symbolic rather than a substantive measure that creates the illusion of erasing their convictions while permitting continued exclusion. Despite being progressive in its examination of discrimination, the court's reasoning leaves significant gaps in how South African law interprets legal rehabilitation of criminal offenders.

Flaw in the Screening Procedures

Lastly, this judgment highlights serious flaws in LexisNexis' screening procedures and the lack of a clear legal framework governing the use of criminal records in employment decision-making. In practice, many employers rely on third-party background check services or automated screening tools. This often leads to automated disqualifications without substantive evaluation of the job's requirements or the candidate's rehabilitation status.

The case illustrates how such practices are contrary to constitutional protections and the objectives of the EEA. The randomness of the screening process is compounded by the fact that the Code of Good Practice on the Integration of Employment Equity into Human Resource Policies and Practices 2005, which warns against collecting and using criminal history unless directly relevant to the advertised position, is not mandatory and few employers treat it as prescriptive.

The result is that candidates with expunged records, like O'Connor, are excluded notwithstanding legislative protections. Hence, this note argues for the establishment of fair vetting practices. South Africa can emulate the US ban-the-box policies, which are part of a larger fair chance employment initiative. These policies prohibit employers from taking criminal records into consideration until the later stages of the hiring process, i.e., when a conditional offer is made. In the event of an unfavourable outcome, employers must provide the applicant with a copy of the background check, explain how the conviction informed the hiring decision, and provide the applicant with an opportunity to make representations (Smith & Simon, 2020). This approach encourages employers to adopt fair chance hiring policies, mainly by deferring background checks until after a conditional offer has been made, to avoid unconscious bias or subjectivity in the initial recruitment stages.

The *O'Connor* case serves both as a warning and a blueprint: a warning against discriminatory hiring practices based on blanket exclusions, and a blueprint for building an employment system that truly embodies the values of South Africa's constitutional order.

Overall, a key contribution of the judgment lies in its assertion that exclusion based on a criminal record is not immune from judicial scrutiny and must be tested against constitutional and statutory principles. Yet, it also highlights the urgent need for reform.

Conclusion

The judgment in *O'Connor* marks a significant development in the protection of job seekers with criminal records. The Labour Court made it clear that past, expunged criminal records cannot serve as a blanket disqualifier for employment in circumstances when the criminal history is irrelevant to the job. The judgment illustrates that employers do not have unlimited discretion in hiring practices. It reaffirms that the constitutional right to dignity comprises the right to rehabilitation and to partake in economic activity.

The *O'Connor* case is a timely reminder that employment equity is not merely about compliance. It is about restoring human dignity, creating second chances, and dismantling systemic barriers to opportunity. In affirming the right of rehabilitated individuals to participate in economic activities, the court took a significant step towards creating a labour market that reflects the ethos of South Africa's constitutional order. However, the note calls for policy reform that would, among others:

- Require written reasons when a candidate with a criminal record, particularly if the record has been expunged or is irrelevant to the job, is overlooked for appointment; and
- Introduce penalties or enforcement measures for employers who contravene anti-discrimination provisions in vetting procedures; and
- Statutory inclusion of discrimination based on criminal records as a form of indirect discrimination.

References

- Criminal Procedure Act 51 of 1977 of South Africa
 Employment Equity Act 55 of 1998 of South Africa
 Harksen v Lane NO 1998 (1) SA 300 (CC)
 Hoffmann v South African Airways, 2001 (1) SA 1 (CC); (2000) 21 ILJ 2357 (CC); [2000] 12 BLLR 1365 (CC)
 Labour Relations Act 66 of 1995 of South Africa
 McGregor, M., Dekker, A., Manamela, M., Manamela, T., & Tshoose, I. (2021). *Labour law rules* (4th ed.). Siber Ink.
 Mujuzi, J. D., & Tsweledi, L. B. (2014). Discrimination on the basis of a criminal record in South Africa: Is having a criminal record an analogous ground? *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 14(3), 244-260.
 Naidoo v Parliament of the Republic of South Africa, (2020) 41 ILJ 1931 (LAC)
 Naylor, B., & Heydon, G. (2022). Criminal records, discrimination, and Aboriginal communities: Enhancing employment opportunities. *Journal of Criminology*, 5(4), 514-531.
 Promotion of National Unity and Reconciliation Act 34 of 1995 of South Africa
 S v Makwanyane, 1995 (3) SA 391 (CC); 1995 (6) BCLR 665 (CC)
 Smith, S. S., & Simon, J. (2020). Exclusion and extraction: Criminal justice contact and the reallocation of labor. *RSF: The Russell Sage Foundation Journal of the Social Sciences*, 6(1), 127.
 Statistics South Africa (2025, May 8) *Youth unemployment rate increases in first quarter of 2025*. Statistics South Africa. <https://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=18028>
 Westrope, E. (2018). Employment discrimination on the basis of criminal history. *The Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 108(2), 367-398.
 White Paper on Corrections in South Africa, 2005

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